

The Development of Pancasila Learning Video using Kinemaster Software for Vocational High School Students

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ABSTRACT: The use of appropriate learning media in Pancasila and civics education subjects will convey various concepts and facts so that students can use and remember longer the teacher's material. This research aims to develop instructional video media to assist students in learning Pancasila and civic education subjects. This research is development research that adopts the development stages of ADDIE. The results showed that the learning videos developed were easy for students to use and had a very high level of attractiveness, and could improve student learning outcomes.

KEYWORDS: Learning video, Kinemaster, Vocational High School, Pancasila Education and Citizenship

I. INTRODUCTION

The learning activity is not just a collection of topics or subject matter of learning material but must be understood and used in a student's daily life. At this time, students are too much burdened with knowledge, but it isn't very meaningful. The knowledge given cannot be used as a support for skills to develop themselves dynamically. As a result, let alone competing, students cannot help themselves learn independently, especially students' understanding of learning materials, including Pancasila and citizenship education.

Students may be able to present a good level of memorization of material received. Still, in reality, they often do not understand this knowledge deeply, so that it is challenging to apply it in life in the classroom, school, and in the community.

A student only has an initial concept in accepting the learning process originating from the phenomena around him. If he agrees with a new idea at school and is the same as the student's initial concept, in the learning process, students can easily accept the learning process. Otherwise, if it contradicts the initial idea, the student will have difficulty and even refuse to study.

The problem now is finding the best learning media capable of conveying various concepts and facts of Pancasila education to easily remember the concept and facts material in the learning process. Pancasila and civics education teachers should have communicated effectively with students who are always actively asking the reasons for something, the meaning of a relationship about what they see in real life, and what they are learning.

Teachers and students primarily determine the success of implementing teaching and learning activities with the integration of teacher activities and student activities. The whole education system is a teaching and learning activity to improve the quality and quantity of teaching and learning activities which is an effort made by the teacher so that teaching and learning interactions occur. Therefore, the main task of a teacher is to create a teaching and learning atmosphere in which it can motivate a student to always learn well with high motivation.

Motivating students in learning will have a very positive impact in achieving optimal learning achievement. Therefore, a teacher must continuously improve his ability to improve the quality and quality of education in the learning process. Teachers have an essential role in improving the quality of learning in class, using learning methods and teaching media. This is so that a student continues to follow the development of learning and does not feel bored with the methods and systems used by a teacher.

A. *The Problem with Pancasila's Teaching*

The researchers' observations have found a lack of student ability due to the lack of motivation in students to study Pancasila and citizenship education material. Also, students consider Pancasila and citizenship education as uninteresting, boring subjects even though they are essential subjects to be used in social, national, and state life.

The lack of interest and motivation is also because the teacher only uses the lecture method during the learning process to be less interested in learning. Besides, the teacher might be less creative in choosing the proper learning methods and strategies

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without using learning media that attract students' interest. However, if the teacher can be creative and apply learning media, it can attract and motivate students in the learning process in the classroom.

The teacher should be able to modify the teaching techniques in the learning process of Pancasila and citizenship education by forming innovative learning without having to eliminate the meaning and purpose of the learning material. Teachers who only provide so much material in the form of lectures are certainly not effective in students' eyes; there need to be innovations that make Pancasila and civic education learning more attractive to students. This is where learning media in teaching activities will make the teaching and learning process packaged into learning is fun and not boring anymore.

B. Learning Video

Pancasila and civics education learning taught in an audiovisual form can attract and direct students' attention. It makes them feel happy with the learning process and be interested and concentrate on teaching and learning activities. To capture the material well and it is easier to remember learning content, it should have a pleasant impression because the ease of placing the material is not only in the form of memorization.

The development of this video learning is suitable to target the learning objectives and material for developing the educational curriculum. Clear concepts are arranged systematically and following essential competencies. The essence of learning media is to become an alternative for teachers not to appear passive and make it easier for teachers to transform material to all students maximally.

Utilizing video media in education will encourage students so that the messages conveyed can be well received and give a deep impression to students. Keep in mind that the video is a media included in the audiovisual media class, acting as a complement. This media is suitable for most students in Surabaya who have computers or smartphones, especially during the distance learning period.

II. RESEARCH METHODS

The research method used is ADDIE Research and Development (R&D) development research. This research was conducted at SMK Negeri 2 (Vocational High School) Surabaya on Tentara Genie Pelajar Number 26, Petemon District, Surabaya. The procedure for the research and development of instructional video media uses the ADDIE research and development procedure, which consists of five steps tailored to the subject and the research field. Namely: 1) Analysis, 2) Design, 3) Development, 4) Implementation, 5) Evaluation.

The research instrument used observation sheets, interview sheets, questionnaire sheets, and evaluation questions to measure students' abilities in understanding the material. The research instrument used a questionnaire for each material expert, media expert, design expert, and peers. The questionnaire in this study was developed based on Nana Sudjana and Ahmad Rivai (2002: 115-119) and Harjanto (2005: 241) criteria about criteria for selecting learning media.

The data analysis technique is qualitative and quantitative in the form of a percentage. Qualitative analysis techniques are used to analyze data from media experts, material experts, design experts, peers, and students' responses. Quantitative analysis is the percentage used to determine data collection results at the initial research stage of individual trials, small group trials, and field trials—drawing conclusions research results based on the analysis of qualitative and quantitative data from various sources.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The research and development activity produces instructional video media products that are attractively packaged to be used in the learning process independently with the help of a smartphone device. The video can be accessed directly through existing smartphone applications such as YouTube and e-learning, not limited by time and space. The fully featured video can be accessed via this link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=YLK9DBKKdYA>

Image 1. The Screenshot of Learning Video Footage

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This learning media is presented together with student's module as well as teacher's module that contains a detailed tutorial on how to make similar video. The student's module is accessible via Google Drive by following this link: <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1kSNiJR405dkLXECgJMXf4xPv0GmfAIyi/view?usp=sharing>

Image 2. Student's Module Footage

The teacher's module that contains step-by-step instruction is accessible via this link: <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1kSNiJR405dkLXECgJMXf4xPv0GmfAIyi/view?usp=sharing>

Image 3. Teacher's Module Footage

The researcher has consulted with some experts and several relevant parties, checks references regarding development research examining various materials about the function and role of Pancasila for the Indonesian nation, discussions with material

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experts, design experts, instructional media experts, and Pancasila and civic education teachers. This development activity is to obtain an assessment and response to the products that have been produced. The summative evaluation is carried out by filling out a closed and open questionnaire and the experts' input.

A. Material Expert Review

The material expert validation results showed that the learning video media for Pancasila and civics education that was developed was stated to be very good in terms of the material aspect with a final assessment score of 89%. It means that the learning video media was feasible to be tested. Material experts provide suggestions and comments on products developed to focus more on the material and the teacher's position to move around.

B. Media Expert Review

The results of media expert validation on this Pancasila learning video were excellent, with a score of 96%. It means that the instructional video media was feasible to be tested. Media experts provide suggestions for a more diverse appearance of writing.

C. Instructional Design Expert Review

The results of the validation of the instructional video media are said to be very good in terms of material sequence and delivery, with an assessment score of 92%. It means that the learning video media of Pancasila material deserves to be tested in real-life teaching.

D. Peer Review

The review by other Pancasila and civics education teachers shows that basically, the products produced are already excellent both in terms of material and design, with a final assessment score of 95%. It means that the learning video media of Pancasila material for the Indonesian nation deserves to be tested. The teacher provides suggestions and comments on products developed to make the sound louder and the background more varied.

E. Individual Trial

Product trials to get input about the validity and reliability of learning activities. This trial was conducted in 1 meeting, namely 2 x 45 minutes. Learning is carried out and guided by distance learning using e-learning which is not limited by time and space. Based on the results of individual trials, it is known that the Pancasila and civics education learning video media developed by researchers received positive responses from students. Overall, the average weighted score of the trial results is 92% that shows excellent feasibility.

F. Small-Group Trial

The small group trial subjects consisted of 10 students with results based on data analysis. The average weighted score of the small group trial results was 88% that shows excellent feasibility as well.

Table 1. Likert Scale Used in Student's Questioner

Score	Percentage	Criteria
4	76% - 100%	Very Feasible
3	51% - 75%	Feasible
2	26% - 50%	Not Feasible
1	0% - 25%	Very Unfeasible

Below, the researchers present the feedback scores from the questioners filled by 10 trial students:

Table 2. The Students' Questioners Report

Feedback Questions	Average Score (%)	Criteria
Have the directions for using the media been clearly conveyed?	75%	Feasible
Is the video on each learning activity in the online class interesting and applicable in conveying the material?	85%	Very Feasible
Is the language used in the video media easy to understand?	85%	Very Feasible
Has the material in this learning video been adjusted in sequence?	90%	Very Feasible
Are the evaluations and the methodology clear enough?	83%	Very Feasible
Are the evaluation questions in accordance with the material being taught?	88%	Very Feasible
By using this media, do you understand more about the material?	78%	Very Feasible

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Does this learning video make you more excited about independent study?	73%	Feasible
Do you have more curiosity about the material being taught with this instructional video?	80%	Very Feasible
Do you feel the applicable benefits for your daily life?	85%	Very Feasible
Average of Total Scores	94%	Very Good

From the table above, we can see that the adult learners who joined the online class trial show very good response and satisfaction, which means that the developed product improves their overall learning experience.

Based on the table above, it can be concluded that the response of students to the media is excellent, meaning that the product developed can enhance their learning experience independently and is very suitable for use.

G. Field Trial

The number of subjects is 35 students. Based on the data, the highest weight score of 100 was achieved by six subjects, while the lowest weight score of 60 was achieved by one subject, and the overall average weighted score of the results of field trials was 85 with excellent criteria.

H. Discussion

The study results indicate that the Pancasila education learning video media and Pancasila citizenship material for the Indonesian people have qualities that help the success of the teaching and learning process. This instructional video media makes students able to study anytime and anywhere students are. In line with the research results from Furi et al. (2017), instructional video media can deliver learning materials that are easily accessible to students anywhere and anytime in the world without being limited by space and time or any educational institution.

The results of this development can also improve learning outcomes and critical thinking skills in students. This is relevant to the research results of Dimas Bayu et al. (2019). Besides, this learning video media can function as a means of information quickly, an easy place, and worldwide.

In the learning system, there are problems in the conventional learning process, but this can be overcome by the sophistication of information and communication technology with the development of instructional video media that can simplify the learning process.

The questionnaire and field trials results show the level of student interest in Pancasila and citizenship education learning materials with the impact of increasing student motivation in learning and learning outcomes. These results are the same as Suwastika's (2018) research that learning media affects student motivation. Marius Panje's (2016) research results show that instructional video media can improve student learning outcomes.

Products developed in the Pancasila and civics education learning video media for vocational students are used individually. Pancasila and citizenship education learning videos are packaged in digital form, digital storage, and uploaded on social media accounts to facilitate access to learning videos.

The overall display design of the product results is made simply with a combination of contrasting colors between the background, text, and images used, making it easier for users to operate. The display of Pancasila and civics education learning videos is made in general, which begins with an opening display and is then followed by explaining KI and KD and the learning objectives that must be achieved.

The Pancasila education learning video media and Pancasila citizenship material for the Indonesian people have several advantages and disadvantages as well as the benefits of this learning video, namely:

Learning video products in digital files and uploading them on YouTube is easy to use and access or duplicate.

The product is also packaged on DVD to prevent viruses.

The material presented is presented in an audio-visual manner and an exciting presentation by providing honest or real examples in students' daily lives.

Meanwhile, this instructional video has drawbacks. (1) this video-based learning guide for Pancasila and citizenship education only discusses Pancasila material for the Indonesian people, and (2) an internet network is required to access learning videos with a prominent enough internet quota because not all students have a supportive quota.

Learning video products have been tested for their effectiveness. Based on the results of field trials, this product has shown its effectiveness by providing results that can improve student learning outcomes. A passing percentage of 85% of field test results have increased learning outcomes.

Learning video media is useful for strengthening memory in the teaching and learning process, motivating students, and doing real learning (Ngure et al., 2014).

A teacher must develop, utilize and have actual knowledge, skills, and experience with creativity in creating the environment and learning needed by students by using learning media. The learning video must contain character values, namely religious, moral

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discipline, creative and innovative logical thinking, and caring for the nation and state's environment. Character is the value of goodness in the form of behavior and actions (Ani, 2014).

Character building in Pancasila and citizenship education is an effort and enthusiasm of students in cultivating character in a comfortable and conducive everyday environment for learning (Hanib et al., 2017). Besides, an attitude of concern for the environment needs to be instilled so that students can appreciate and protect God's creation more (Puspitasari et al., 2016).

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the research results, the learning video media developed were declared valid and usable. Pancasila education learning video media and Pancasila citizenship material for the Indonesian nation can provide reinforcement and knowledge and facilitate the teaching and learning process to help students understand learning material more efficiently. Based on the discussion, it can be described that the learning video product developed is very suitable for use based on the results of the material expert validation assessment obtained a percentage calculation of 89%. Based on the assessment results of the instructional video media expert validation, the percentage calculation was 96%. Based on the expert validation assessment of instructional media designs, the percentage calculation is 92%. Based on the peer-to-peer validation assessment results for Pancasila and civics education teachers, the percentage calculation is 95%. The percentage of data analysis results that have been compared with predetermined criteria shows that the development of learning videos is included in the good standards in terms of convenience. Based on the processing of individual trial data, the percentage was 92%. Finally, small group trials gained an 88% score while its field trials received 85%.

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